

METHODS FOR OBTAINING OIL FROM COTTON

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05.01.08 –Texnologik jarayonlar va ishlab
chiqarishlarni avtomatlashtirish va boshqarish
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Annotation: Obtaining oil from cotton typically refers to extracting cottonseed oil—which comes from the seeds of the cotton plant. The process of extracting oil from cottonseed involves several key methods. However, mechanical pressing methods (such as expeller pressing) are preferred in smaller-scale operations or for producing oils with minimal processing. Newer techniques, such as enzyme-assisted extraction and supercritical CO₂ extraction, are gaining traction for their eco-friendliness and higher quality results.

Keywords: cotton, process, methods, extraction, traction, Mechanical Pressing, Cold Pressing, Expeller Pressing, Disadvantages, Solvent Extraction, Enzyme-Assisted Extraction, Hydraulic Pressing, Pressurized Liquid Extraction.

1. Mechanical Pressing (Cold Pressing or Expeller Pressing) This is a more traditional method of extracting oil from cottonseeds, which involves using mechanical force to crush the seeds and extract the oil.

Cold Pressing: The cottonseeds are mechanically pressed at low temperatures. This method preserves the nutrients in the oil but typically yields a lower quantity of oil.

Expeller Pressing: A screw-type mechanical press is used to apply high pressure to the seeds to extract the oil. This method generates some heat, but it doesn't reach the high temperatures of refining, allowing the oil to retain much of its flavor and nutritional properties.

Advantages:

Retains more natural flavors and nutrients (especially in cold pressing). More natural, with minimal chemical use.

Disadvantages:

Lower oil yield compared to solvent extraction. Requires specialized equipment.

2. Solvent Extraction (Chemical Extraction)

Solvent extraction is the most common method used in industrial settings for extracting oil from cottonseeds due to its high efficiency in obtaining oil.

Process: The seeds are first ground into a fine meal. A solvent like hexane is then used to dissolve the oil from the meal. The solvent and oil mixture is then heated to evaporate the solvent, leaving behind the oil.

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Volume 2 Issue 17 Dekabr 2024

Refining: After solvent extraction, the crude cottonseed oil typically undergoes a refining process to remove impurities such as free fatty acids, pigments, and other unwanted substances.

Advantages:

High oil yield (up to 99% of the oil can be extracted). Suitable for large-scale industrial production.

Disadvantages:

Involves chemicals (solvent) that can leave trace residues if not properly removed. More complex and expensive due to the need for solvent recovery and refining processes.

3. Enzyme-Assisted Extraction

This is a newer, more advanced method that uses enzymes to break down the cell walls of the cottonseeds and release oil more efficiently. **Process:** Enzymes such as cellulases or pectinases are used to break down the cottonseed's cellular structure, making it easier to release the oil. This method can be combined with mechanical pressing or solvent extraction.

Advantages: This method can improve oil yield and is considered more eco-friendly compared to using solvents.

Advantages: Can improve oil yield compared to traditional pressing methods. Environmentally friendly, as it may reduce the need for solvents.

Disadvantages: Relatively more expensive and still not as widely adopted as mechanical or solvent extraction methods.

4. Supercritical Fluid Extraction (CO₂ Extraction)

This method uses supercritical carbon dioxide (CO₂) as a solvent to extract oil from cottonseeds. Process: CO₂ is used in its supercritical state (where it acts both as a liquid and gas) to extract oil from the cottonseeds. After extraction, the CO₂ is separated from the oil and recycled for further use.

Advantages:

Very clean extraction method, with no chemical residues. Produces a high-quality, high-purity oil.

Considered environmentally friendly, as CO₂ is a natural solvent.

Disadvantages: Expensive and requires specialized equipment. Lower yield compared to solvent extraction.

5. Hydraulic Pressing (Traditional Manual Pressing)

This is a less common method, particularly in industrial settings, but still used in small-scale or artisanal operations.

Process: Cottonseeds are placed in a hydraulic press, where high pressure is applied to extract oil. The process is slower and yields less oil compared to other methods.

Advantages: Minimal processing; retains more natural compounds. No chemical solvents used.

Disadvantages: Very low yield and labor-intensive. Typically used for small batches rather than large-scale production.

6. Ultrasonic Extraction

This is an innovative, less conventional method of extracting oil using ultrasonic waves.

Process: High-frequency sound waves are applied to the cottonseed to create microscopic bubbles in the oil, which helps break down the seed structure and release the oil.

Advantages: High efficiency and reduced use of chemicals. Short extraction time.

Disadvantages: Still relatively new and not widely used in commercial settings. Equipment costs can be high.

7. Hydrodistillation (Steam Distillation)

Hydrodistillation is a method that uses steam to extract oil, commonly employed in essential oil extraction but can also be applied to cottonseed oil extraction.

Process: The cottonseeds are subjected to steam, causing the oil to vaporize. Once the vapor cools,

the oil condenses and can be collected. This process works by utilizing the volatility of the oil components.

Advantages:

Uses no solvents, making it an environmentally friendly method. Can extract some volatile compounds that may not be captured by other methods.

Disadvantages:

Low yield compared to solvent extraction and mechanical pressing. The process is typically slower and may not be suitable for large-scale production. Requires careful control of steam temperature to avoid degradation of the oil.

8. Pressurized Liquid Extraction (PLE)

Pressurized Liquid Extraction is a method that uses high pressure and moderate heat to extract oils and other bioactive compounds from seeds and plant materials.

Process: Cottonseeds are subjected to high-pressure liquid solvents (such as ethanol or hexane) in a closed system. The high pressure helps to penetrate the seed cells, and the liquid solvent extracts the oil. The solvent is then separated and recycled, and the oil is collected.

Advantages:

Faster extraction process compared to traditional methods. Can achieve higher extraction yields. Can use less toxic solvents (e.g., ethanol) instead of petroleum-based solvents.

Disadvantages:

Requires specialized equipment capable of handling high-pressure conditions. More costly than basic mechanical pressing or solvent extraction.

9. Molecular Distillation

Molecular distillation is a form of vacuum distillation that can be used to refine and purify oils, particularly for specialized purposes like the extraction of high-purity cottonseed oil. Process: This method uses extremely low pressures to distill the oil at lower temperatures, which helps to avoid thermal degradation. The oil is separated from the other components based on differences in molecular size and volatility.

Advantages:

Removes volatile impurities, ensuring high-purity oil. Retains the oil's beneficial compounds and nutritional properties.

Disadvantages: High energy consumption. Requires advanced equipment and a high level of expertise. Primarily used in the refining process rather than the extraction of crude oil.

Conclusion. The most commonly used method for extracting oil from cottonseeds is solvent extraction, due to its high oil yield and efficiency. However, mechanical pressing methods (such as expeller pressing) are preferred in smaller-scale operations or for producing oils with minimal processing. Newer techniques, such as enzyme-assisted extraction and supercritical CO₂ extraction, are gaining traction for their eco-friendliness and higher quality results. The method chosen depends on factors such as production scale, desired oil quality, and cost considerations.

There are many innovative and emerging techniques for extracting oil from cottonseeds,

ranging from more traditional mechanical pressing and solvent extraction methods to advanced and environmentally friendly approaches such as microwave-assisted extraction, superheated steam, and fermentation-assisted extraction. While solvent extraction remains the industry standard due to its efficiency, these alternative methods are gaining attention for their sustainability, efficiency, and ability to preserve the quality of the oil.

The choice of method depends on various factors including scale of production, desired oil quality, energy consumption, and environmental impact considerations. Newer techniques, especially those focused on "green" methods (e.g., microwave-assisted and supercritical CO₂ extraction), are likely to play an increasing role in the future of oil extraction as the demand for sustainable practices grows.

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